

DEEP LEARNING MODELS FOR FORECASTING TREASURY BILL RATES USING GASOLINE PRICES AND GOLD EPI

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence has given researchers access to a broader range of historical data, enabling the development of more accurate predictive models in finance. This study investigates the relationship between treasury bill rates and two high-demand commodities: gasoline and gold. We compiled a comprehensive dataset spanning ten years of historical prices, from July 2014 to July 2024, consisting of treasury bill rates, gasoline prices, gold-EPI, and natural gas consumption, as well as vital economic indicators such as GDP, inflation rates, and interest rates.

Our analysis reveals that natural gas consumption exhibits the highest positive correlation (0.64) with treasury bill rates, while gasoline prices and the gold export price index show moderate positive correlations (0.51 and 0.52, respectively). Training the data on a machine learning model (Artificial Neural Network) and three deep learning models (Recurrent Neural Network, Convolutional Neural Network, and 3D Convolutional Neural Network). Their performance was assessed using mean absolute error, mean squared error, root mean squared error (RMSE), and R-squared score. The Recurrent Neural Network model performed best with an RMSE of 0.08.

Key Words: Deep Learning, Recurrent Neural Network, Treasury Bill Rate, 3D Convolutional Neural Network, Artificial Neural Network, Machine Learning

1. Introduction

Treasury bill rates serve as crucial indicators of economic health and influence investment strategies across financial markets. This is rooted in the connection of Treasury Bills (T-bills) to monetary policy, investment strategies, and macroeconomic planning. Accurate prediction of Treasury bill rates enables better financial planning and risk management.

Previously, traditional models for predicting Treasury Bills have depended on historical interest rate data and macroeconomic indicators. However, modern research studies have investigated the predictive power of commodity prices and uncertainty indices, such as those related to gasoline prices, in forecasting financial variables.

1.1 Treasury Bill Rate Forecasting

T-bill rates are short-term government securities that reflect prevailing monetary conditions. [1] explore variations of the Nelson–Siegel yield curve as a dynamic model that achieves dimensionality reduction via factor structure (level, slope, and curvature). Their results reiterated the importance of macroeconomic variables. Commodity markets have been seen to play key roles in shaping interest rate expectations. [2] show that uncertainty in the U.S. Treasury market, measured via a VIX-style index for 10-year Treasury futures, significantly predicts crude oil price movements and volatility. They found that oil prices react negatively to an increase in uncertainty

about future interest rates, which in turn leads to an increase in the volatility of oil prices. Their findings suggest that, in addition to the level of rates, interest rate uncertainty can also influence commodity prices, which in turn affect inflation expectations and monetary policy responses.

1.2 Gasoline Prices as Economic Indicators

Gasoline prices, shaped by global oil markets, geopolitical tensions, and supply-demand dynamics, are vital indicators of inflation in the economy. These prices reflect broader economic trends, as they are influenced by factors such as Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) production decisions, sanctions on oil-exporting nations, and disruptions caused by conflicts or natural disasters. As gasoline costs fluctuate, they impact transportation expenses and the prices of goods and services across all sectors, making them crucial barometers of economic health and inflationary pressures. [3] and [4] provided empirical evidence linking oil price shocks to macroeconomic fluctuations, suggesting that gasoline prices can indirectly affect interest rates through inflation expectations and central bank responses.

1.3 Gold Prices and Economic Policy Uncertainty

Gold has historically been viewed as a safe-haven asset during periods of economic instability. [5] analyzed the role of gold in the global financial system they found that gold plays a significant role as a hedge against uncertainty. [6] developed the EPU index to quantify economic policy-related uncertainty. The Gold EPU, a composite measure integrating gold price movements with policy uncertainty, may capture investor sentiment and risk aversion, both of which influence interest rate expectations.

The interaction between commodity prices and interest rates has been explored through various econometric and machine learning models. [7] In their book, they present a case for hybrid models that combine statistical and machine learning techniques to enhance forecasting accuracy. Artificial intelligence has given researchers access to a broader range of historical data, enabling the development of more accurate predictive models in finance.

Models such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Gated Recurrent Units (GRU), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), and Transformers are increasingly used due to their ability to capture nonlinear and temporal dependencies.

[8] reviewed deep learning models for financial forecasting and highlighted the superiority of deep architectures like Transformers, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), and Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) in modeling complex financial relationships. They found that these models performed better than traditional statistical models, such as the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model, in capturing volatility and regime shifts in financial markets.

[9] conducted a rigorous comparison of DL models (CNN, LSTM, GRU) for predicting short-term and long-term Treasury yields. They found that LSTM and GRU models performed best in capturing the dynamics of the yield curve.

Although there is vast literature on interest rate forecasting and commodity price analysis, limited research has directly examined the joint influence of gasoline prices and the Gold EPU on T-bill rates.

This study leverages deep learning models to capture complex relationships between Treasury bill rates and various macroeconomic factors.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: in Section 2, we provide details on the properties of the out models that were employed and model evaluation techniques. Section 3 describes the data and some exploratory analysis of the data. Results are presented in Section 4, and Section 5 concludes. All the analyses are done using the Python software [10].

2. Methods

2.1 The models

The data was trained on a machine learning model (Artificial Neural Network) and three deep learning models, viz, Recurrent Neural Network, Convolutional Neural Network, and 3D Convolutional Neural Network. We give more details about each of these models below.

2.1.1 Artificial Neural Network

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are computer systems designed to simulate the human brain's information processing capabilities. In the same way, the human brain uses neurons to process data and make decisions; ANNs use artificial neurons to analyze data, identify patterns, and make predictions. These networks comprise layers of interconnected neurons that work together to solve complex problems. The key idea is that ANNs can "learn" from the data they process, just as our brain learns from experience. They are used in various applications from recognizing images to making personalized recommendations.

The ANN consists of the

- Input Layer where the network receives information.
- Hidden Layers where data is received from the input layer and processed. The more hidden layers there are, the more complex patterns the network can learn and understand. Each hidden layer transforms the data into more abstract information.
- Output Layer where the final decision or prediction is made. [11]

Figure 1: ANN Layers- <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/artificial-intelligence/artificial-neural-networks-and-its-applications/>

2.1.2 Recurrent Neural Network

RNNs are a type of neural network specifically designed to process sequential data [12]. An RNN model has a recurrent connection that enables information to flow from the previous steps to the current step, thereby capturing the temporal dependencies between data points at different positions in the sequence.

The fundamental processing unit in RNN is a Recurrent Unit. They hold a hidden state that maintains information about previous inputs in a sequence. Recurrent units can "remember" information from prior steps by feeding back their hidden state, allowing them to find dependencies across time.

In RNNs, the hidden state H_i is calculated for every input X_i to retain sequential dependencies. The computations follow these core formulas:

$$h = \sigma(U \cdot X + W \cdot h_{t-1} + B)$$

Where h represents the current hidden state, U and W are weight matrices, and B is the bias. The output Y is calculated by applying O an activation function to the weighted hidden state where V and C represents weights and bias. i.e. $Y = O(V \cdot h + C)$, where $Y = f(X, h, W, U, V, B, C)$. This function defines the entire RNN operation, where the state matrix S holds each element s_i representing the network's state at each time step i .

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Figure 2: <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/machine-learning/introduction-to-recurrent-neural-network/>

2.1.3 Convolutional Neural Network

The ability of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to discover significant patterns in sequential data has made them suitable candidates for adapting to time series forecasting. In contrast to conventional time series models that depend on manually designed features, CNNs autonomously acquire hierarchical representations via convolutional processes. Mathematically, the convolution operation is expressed as follows:

$$Z_i = \sum_{j=0}^k \mathfrak{N}_{i+j} \mathcal{W}_j + b, \quad (1)$$

Where: Z_i =output of the convolutional layer.

\mathfrak{N}_{i+j} = input sequence.

\mathcal{W}_j = filter (kernel) weights.

b = bias term.

k =kernel size.

After convolution, the model is trained using a non-linear activation function. The function appends the data with non-linear features to enable the model to engage with complicated statistical patterns. Applying a pooling layer helps decrease dimensionality while preserving vital information. Max pooling is a popular technique, described as follows:

$$p = \max (Z_i + Z_{i+1} + \dots + Z_{i+k}) \quad (2)$$

The calculation involves the window size parameter k . The processed feature maps

from the convolutional and pooling layers become a one-dimensional vector, after which the network sends them to the fully connected layer. This process is called flattening. The extracted features are then directed to fully connected layers for making final predictions. Figure 1 presents the complete architecture design of the CNN model.

Figure 3: <https://www.programming-ocean.com/ai-architectures/CNN-architecture.php>

2.1.4 3D Convolutional Neural Network

3-dimensional convolutional neural network (3D CNN) Models have become increasingly popular. Recently, researchers have been exploring best practices in extending the image recognition capacity of CNN models to financial data, aiming to identify patterns in image data and create predictive models from these patterns. [13] applied convolutional neural networks on graphs to predict the future outlook based on the current prices. The financial data was first converted into graphs, and then the graphs, which are now our image data, are placed into the CNN algorithm for learning and forecasting. [14] also trained the CNN model along with other models on Forex data. The most common image data currently used for CNN prediction is the candlestick graph. used this traditional candlestick method in his Forex analysis. There is a strong argument that the CNN models outperform other simpler models.

2.2 Model Performance Analysis

The Models' performance was assessed using mean absolute error, mean squared error, root mean squared error (RMSE), and R-squared score.

Below are further details on each of these model evaluation techniques.

- Mean Absolute Error (MAE), computes the mean absolute deviation between actual and predicted values.
- Mean Squared Error (MSE) quantifies the average squared deviation between observed and predicted values.
- Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) quantifies the square root of the mean of the squared deviations between actual and predicted values.
- R-squared score (R^2) quantifies the extent to which the model incorporates the variation in the actual data. A value closer to 1 indicates a strong predictive capability.

Table 1 below presents the mathematicians' formations for these performance measures.

Table 1: mathematicians' formations for these performance measures

Performance Measure	Mathematical Formular
MAE	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x - \hat{x} $
MSE	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x - \hat{x})^2$
RMSE	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x - \hat{x})^2}$
R ²	$1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x - \hat{x})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (x - \bar{x})^2}$

Where x_i represents the actual values, \hat{x} denotes the predicted value, and \bar{x} is the mean.

3. Data

3.1 Data Collection

The data used in this study is a comprehensive dataset spanning from July 2014 to July 2024 (excluding weekends and federal holidays) collected from the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis' Federal Reserve Economic Data (FRED) application programming interface (api). The dataset comprises 2,610 daily observations of treasury bill rates along with six economic indicators that were selected based on their theoretical relationship to interest rate movements. The data represents a complete time series of market days during this period, providing sufficient temporal coverage to capture multiple economic cycles.

The primary target variable, treasury bill rates, was collected alongside predictor variables including effective federal funds rates, ten-year inflation expectations, gross domestic product figures, regular gasoline prices, natural gas consumption data, and gold export price indices. Each variable was sourced directly from official financial market data providers to ensure accuracy and reliability.

Data extraction was performed through automated processes that accessed the FRED API. The collection methodology prioritized daily frequency data where available, with some economic indicators like GDP requiring interpolation from quarterly releases to maintain temporal consistency across the dataset. We aligned quarterly data with daily frequency using forward-fill expansion.

Initial data assessment revealed that there were missing values concentrated in three key variables, with treasury bill rates, interest rates, and inflation rates each showing 108 missing observations, while GDP showed 6 missing values, and gas prices had 3 missing observations. Natural gas consumption and gold export price index data were complete with no missing values due to forward-fill expansion. The missing data pattern appeared to be systematic rather than random, indicating that it corresponded to federal holidays and weekends when financial markets were closed.

To prepare the data, listwise deletion was used to delete all observations with missing values. The final cleaned dataset was 2,501 observations. This approach maintains the integrity of the time series structure while ensuring the predictive models are trained on complete cases. The reduction from 2,610 to 2,501 observations represents a 4.2% data loss, which is considered acceptable for the scope of this analysis and is unlikely to significantly impact the robustness of the findings.

3.2 Exploratory Data Analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis revealed significant variability in treasury bill rates over the study period, with values ranging from near zero during the pandemic-induced economic uncertainty in 2020 to peaks exceeding 5.2% during the 2024 period of monetary policy tightening. The mean treasury bill rate across the entire period was approximately 1.8% with a standard deviation of 1.9%, reflecting the significant monetary policy shifts that occurred during this timeframe. The distribution showed clear temporal clustering, with extended periods of extremely low rates followed by rapid increases during policy normalization phases.

Figure 4: Line plot of treasury bill rates overtime.

The visualization of treasury bill rates in Figure 4 shows dramatic structural changes in treasury bill rate behavior, most notably the sharp decline to near-zero levels in March 2020 corresponding to Federal Reserve emergency policy responses to the COVID-19 pandemic. Rates remained at historically low levels through early 2022 before beginning a steep upward trajectory that continued through the end of the study period. This pattern reflects the broader macroeconomic environment, including quantitative easing implementation and subsequent monetary policy normalization efforts.

Correlation analysis identified several strong relationships between treasury bill rates and the economic predictors, with interest rates showing the highest correlation coefficient of 0.995, indicating an almost perfect positive relationship. GDP demonstrated a strong positive correlation of 0.776, while natural gas consumption showed a moderate correlation of 0.644. Gas prices and gold export price indices exhibited moderate positive correlations of 0.511 and 0.517, respectively, while inflation rates showed the weakest relationship with a correlation of 0.403.

The correlation matrix visualization in Figure 5 revealed potential multicollinearity concerns, particularly between treasury bill rates and interest rates, which was expected given that these represent closely related monetary policy instruments. The heatmap analysis showed that while most predictor variables demonstrated positive correlations with the target variable, the strength of these relationships varied considerably, suggesting that some variables may provide more predictive power than others in a multivariate modeling context.

Figure 5: Heatmap correlation matrix visualizing the relationship between each variable.

Feature engineering decisions were based on these correlation findings, with the selection of five primary predictor variables: interest rates, inflation rates, GDP, gas prices, natural gas consumption, and gold export price indices. These variables were chosen because they demonstrated at least moderate correlations with treasury bill rates and represent different aspects of economic activity that could theoretically influence monetary policy decisions. Data preprocessing included standardization using z-score normalization to ensure equal contribution across features with different scales and units, which is particularly important for neural network architectures that are sensitive to input magnitude differences.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Results

The experimental design employed a stratified 80-20 train-test split. Four neural network models were implemented and compared: an Artificial Neural Network (ANN), a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), a three-dimensional Convolutional Neural Network (3D CNN), and a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) architecture. Each model was optimized individually using different hyperparameter configurations to maximize performance.

The Recurrent Neural Network pictured in Figure 6 achieved the most superior performance across all evaluation metrics. It achieved a mean absolute error of 0.059, mean squared error of 0.008, root mean squared error of 0.092, and R-squared value of 0.998. These results indicate exceptional predictive accuracy. The RNN architecture's ability to capture temporal dependencies in the sequential data appears to be particularly well-suited for this financial forecasting task.

Figure 6: Scatterplot visualization of the actual and projected treasury bill rates using the RNN model.

The Convolutional Neural Network pictured in Figure 7 had the second-best performance. It achieved a mean absolute error of 0.095, a mean squared error of 0.021, a root mean squared error of 0.146, and an R-squared value of 0.994. This strong performance suggests that CNN architectures, despite being commonly associated with image classification, can effectively identify patterns in economic time-series data. The CNN's ability to detect feature combinations through its convolutional layers proved valuable for capturing relationships between economic variables.

Figure 7: Scatterplot visualization of the actual and projected treasury bill rates using the CNN model.

The Artificial Neural Network pictured in Figure 8 achieved a solid but lower performance. It had a mean absolute error of 0.284, mean squared error of 0.168, root mean squared error of 0.411, and R-squared value of 0.951. While the model still displayed strong predictive capability with an R-squared above 0.95, the feedforward architecture showed limitations in capturing the temporal structure present in the time series data. The higher error metrics suggest that the ANN may be less effective at modeling the dynamic relationships between economic indicators and treasury bill rates.

Figure 8: Scatterplot visualization of the actual and projected treasury bill rates using the ANN model.

The three-dimensional Convolutional Neural Network pictured in Figure 9 showed mixed performance with a mean absolute error of 0.202, mean squared error of 0.075, root mean squared error of 0.273, and R-squared value of 0.978. The 3D CNN architecture, while innovative in its approach to structuring the input data in spatial dimensions, did not demonstrate clear advantages over simpler architectures for this prediction task. The complexity of the 3D convolutions may have been unnecessary given the relatively straightforward nature of the economic indicator relationships.

Figure 9: Scatterplot visualization of the actual and projected treasury bill rates using the 3D CNN model.

4.2 Discussion

These results demonstrate that deep learning models can achieve exceptionally high accuracy in predicting treasury bill rates using readily available economic indicators, with all four architectures achieving R-squared values above 0.95. The superior performance of the RNN model shows the model's capability in capturing patterns in financial time series data using its ability to capture temporal dependencies. The model's ability to maintain information about previous economic conditions while processing current indicators appears crucial for accurate rate prediction.

The strong performance of the CNN model reveals an interesting finding about the applicability of convolutional architectures to financial time series data. The CNN's success suggests that local patterns and feature combinations within the economic indicator space contain significant predictive information about treasury bill movements. This challenges the notion that CNNs are primarily

useful for spatial data, demonstrating their potential value in identifying sequential patterns within economic datasets.

The correlation analysis findings are particularly significant in understanding model behavior, with the near-perfect correlation between treasury bill rates and interest rates (0.995) suggesting that the effective federal funds rate serves as an extremely strong predictor. This relationship is a result of both rates being monetary policy controlled by the Federal Reserve. The moderate correlations observed for GDP, natural gas consumption, gas prices, and gold prices indicate these variables provide additional predictive signal beyond the primary interest rate relationship.

However, there are several limitations in this study that must be addressed. The ten-year period was selected to capture several economic cycles, but it may not have been able to capture the full range of economic conditions that could affect model generalizability. Given the exceptionally high R-squared values across the models, there is concern for overfitting. The R-squared values are a result of the chosen parameters. Interest rates showed a near-perfect correlation with treasury bill rates, leading to the model having a stronger performance. The model heavily depends on interest rate data for accuracy. The models also have a subpar performance during economic uncertainty compared to their performance during regular economic conditions.

5. Conclusion and Future Research

This study employed the Artificial Neural Network, Recurrent Neural Network, Convolutional Neural Network, and 3D Convolutional Neural Network to explain complex relationships between Treasury bill rates and various macroeconomic factors. The model performance was assessed using the mean absolute error, the mean squared error, the root mean squared error (RMSE), and the R-squared score. The Recurrent Neural Network model performed best with an RMSE of 0.08. The analysis further reveals that natural gas consumption exhibits the highest positive correlation (0.64) with treasury bill rates, while gasoline prices and the gold export price index show moderate positive correlations (0.51 and 0.52, respectively).

For practical implementation, these models could provide valuable insights for financial institutions, policy makers, and investors seeking to anticipate treasury bill rate movements. However, using the models would require careful consideration of model drift over time, particularly during periods of significant monetary policy changes. The models' reliance on interest rate data suggests they may be less effective during periods when the relationship between federal funds rates and treasury bill rates becomes decoupled due to market stress.

This research could be expanded to include additional high-demand commodities, e.g., cash crops. In addition, other types of recurrent and neural network models can be considered.

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